

A New General Method for Synthesis of *o*-Aldehydo-carboxylic Acids. A Preliminary Note.

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There are very few really good methods available for the synthesis of substituted *o*-aldehydo acids. Thus the majority of the monomethoxy- and dimethoxy-*o*-aldehydo acids have either still to be synthesised or have been synthesised by methods which are either not of general application or are too tedious. At the time when these researches were started, only *m*-opianic acid and opianic acid had been synthesised. The synthesis of *m*-opianic acid was first accomplished by Perkin and Fargher (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1724) in accordance with the scheme:—

Unfortunately this excellent synthesis cannot be generally applied, firstly because it is very difficult to introduce the acetyl group in the required position and secondly, because the oxidation of substances of the type (II) give rise to a variety of different products which are often difficult to separate. Reimer-Tiemann's reaction cannot also be used as a general method for the synthesis of *o*-aldehydo acids (*cf.* Perkin and Stoye, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3172).

The only other method which has been tried successfully is the method of the oxidation of phthalides. Thus opianic acid has been obtained by the oxidation of meconine.

This method is, also, of only limited application as is shown by the failure of attempts of direct oxidation of ψ -meconine (Solomon, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 888; Edward, Perkin and Stoye, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 196; Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 208), of 3:4-

methoxylenedioxyphthalide (Perkin and Trikofus, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2931), of 4:5-methylenedioxyphthalide (Stevens and Robertson, *ibid.*, 1927, 2791) and of 4-methoxyphthalide (Chakravarti and Perkin *ibid.*, 1929, 197). The present author tried a number of devices to get over this difficulty (*loc. cit.*, p. 209). In the case of ψ -meconine, more recently still, Robinson and Greenwood succeeded in converting it into ψ -opianic acid by first converting ψ -meconine into β - ψ -gnoscopine and then oxidising it (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1371)

The present author tried to devise a number of general methods for synthesising methoxy-*o*-aldehydo acids in 1928. As a result of this and subsequent work, two general methods have been developed, one starting from the hydrindones, and the other from the substituted derivatives of naphthalene. In the latter method, symmetrically disubstituted or symmetrically tetrasubstituted naphthalene derivatives are oxidised with alkaline permanganate under special conditions. To take an example, when 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene (V) is oxidised, 5-methoxyphthalonic acid (VI) is first formed which is readily converted into 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid (VII)

The idea behind the synthesis is that whichever benzene ring is ruptured during oxidation, a methoxyphthalonic acid must be formed under suitable conditions. A number of such synthesis has been effected and an account of the synthesis of all the methoxyphthalaldehydic acids and the three opianic acids by this method is reserved for a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

As a result of a series of comparative experiments, the following two conditions of oxidation were arrived at as giving the best yields of the substituted phthalaldehydic acids.

(i) A mixture of the substituted naphthalene (1 mol.), sodium hydroxide (1 mol.), 6% aqueous potassium permanganate solution (3 mol.) were heated together with constant shaking till decolorised (3 to 4 hours). The oxidation was generally effected in 20 g-wts.

(ii) In a 2 litre flask provided with a good mechanical stirrer, a reflux apparatus and a dropping funnel, the substituted naphthalene derivative (0.25 mol.) was suspended in 2% solution of sodium hydroxide (250 c.c.) and the mixture heated to boiling. To the boiling solution was added gradually during the course of 2 hours a hot 10% aqueous potassium permanganate solution (2.3/8 mols). After the last addition of permanganate, the mixture was boiled for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to complete the oxidation.

The oxidation product was generally worked up as described below in the case of 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene. Yields of the final *o*-aldehydo acids vary from 15 to 40%. Oxidations under condition (i) generally give larger quantities of the phthalic acids, although the net yield of the substituted *o*-aldehydo acids is as good, if not better as under the condition (ii). Under condition (ii), more of the starting substance is left unoxidised. For obtaining the best yields it is necessary to have the naphthalene derivative in as pure a state as possible.

During these experiments it has been found that if the object is to synthesise the aldehydo acids, it is not at all necessary to isolate the substituted phthalonic acids, as the aldehydo acids crystallise much better.

Preparation of 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene.—2:6-Dihydroxynaphthalene was prepared and purified according to the directions given by Willstätter and Parans (*Ber.*, 1907 40, 1410). Pure 2:6-dihydroxynaphthalene was converted into 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene in almost quantitative yields by carrying out the methylation with dimethylsulphate in methyl alcohol solution, sodium hydroxide solution being added gradually from time to time so as to keep the solution just alkaline.

Oxidation of 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene was carried out as described under (i) and (ii). After the oxidation was over, the mixture

was cooled and the precipitated manganese dioxide and the unchanged substance were filtered off. The filtrate was made just acid with concentrated hydrochloric acid and then evaporated to dryness. The residue was then dissolved in water, the solution neutralised and treated with excess of sodium bisulphite (generally for 1 mol. of the naphthalene, 2 mol. of the bisulphite were used) and evaporated to dryness on the steam-bath and then the residue heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at 120° in an air oven. The residue thus obtained was then twice stirred up with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on the steam-bath in an open dish. This residue was then extracted twice with boiling benzene and the combined benzene extract allowed to remain for a few hours when small amount of substance (A) rapidly separated. The filtrate from this was concentrated to a small volume and allowed to crystallise. A crystalline substance soon separates, the melting point of which in crude state is 125° . On repeated crystallisation from water, the substance separated in beautiful rosettes of needles, m.p. 144° . This substance is 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid. (Found: C, 59.9, 59.8; H, 4.4, 4.3. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 4.4 per cent). The identity of this substance was established by taking the mixed melting point with 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid obtained from 5-methoxyphthalonic acid. It also forms an oxime.

The substance (A) was found to be very sparingly soluble in benzene and very readily so in cold water. On reboiling with benzene it melts at about 150° and is probably impure 4-methoxyphthalic acid. It is also likely that the mother liquors from 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid may contain small amounts of 4-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid. This point is being further investigated.

In a preliminary experiment attempts were made to isolate the phthalonic acid first. But this acid does not crystallise readily and is difficult to isolate in view of the fact that it is far more soluble in water than in benzene. An aqueous solution of the phthalonic acid obtained from 2:6-dimethoxynaphthalene was treated with an acetic acid solution of phenylhydrazine when on vigorous stirring and allowing to remain a pale yellow crystalline substance separated, m.p. 200° . On repeated recrystallisations yellow coloured needles, m.p. 223° were obtained. This substance was found to be identical with 6-methoxy-3-phenyl-phthalozon (4) carboxylic acid (1) obtained from 5-phthalonic acid by the method of mixed melting points.

Synthesis of 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid was effected according to the conditions described before (Chakravarti and Perkin, *loc. cit.*, p. 199). It was then oxidised to 5-methoxyphthalonic acid by the method of Fritsch (*Annalen*, 1897, 296, 359). 5-Methoxyphthalonic acid (11.5 g.) was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution (5.6 g. in 55 c.c.), and the solution evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 40% sodium bisulphite solution (40-50 c.c.) and evaporated to dryness on the water-bath. This residue was heated for an hour at 120° and then treated twice with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution evaporated to dryness. The residue was completely extracted with benzene. On concentrating the benzene solution and allowing to stand, a crystalline substance was deposited. On being recrystallised twice from water 5-methoxyphthalaldehydic acid separated in beautiful needles, m.p. 144°. (Found: C, 59.9; H, 4.3. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 4.4 per cent).

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